

Type and level of production provided by the requestor

Type of production: broiler

Level: husbandry

Keywords: behaviour, health and body condition, management, mutilation, skeletal damage

Background context provided by the requestor

This query concerns cannibalism, the causative factors and management in free range broiler systems (slaughtered at 56 days + old).

Question raised by the requestor

What preventative measures can be taken to avoid cannibalism outbreaks in broiler flocks, including free-range flocks?

Answer

Cannibalism in poultry production refers to forms of injurious pecking that involve pecks to the skin, vent, or toes (Rodenburg et al., 2013). Cannibalism can develop from accidental injuries, vent pecking, and severe feather pecking (SFP) due to the appearance of blood which can stimulate cannibalistic pecking (Temple et al., 2017). Due to the close connection between SFP and cannibalism, in this query we assume that these behaviours share biological mechanisms and that prevention strategies for SFP will consequently also prevent cannibalism.

This problem is predominant in poultry species or categories with longer production cycles (i.e., laying hens, turkeys), and is therefore less common in conventional broiler flocks that have commonly shorter lifespan. For example, in laying hens, severe feather pecking can occur anytime during the rearing period but often increases as hens reach sexual maturity (EFSA, 2023). As such, there is a lack of literature on cannibalism in broiler flocks, although this is a growing area of interest due to the increased use of slower-growing broiler genotypes that live longer in alternative systems, whereas fast-growing genotypes are usually slaughtered before reaching sexual maturity.

Due to the multifactorial nature of SFP and cannibalism, it is difficult to determine exactly which conditions are most likely to prevent it occurring. In this document, we review the broiler literature when available, otherwise, we assume the preventive measures for SFP and cannibalism are the same across poultry species and briefly review findings from species such as laying hens and turkeys.

Bird-Level Prevention Strategies

Beak trimming

Intact beaks have a much greater potential for feather and tissue damage when birds peck each other. Therefore, a potential prevention strategy is beak trimming. Beak trimming does not prevent pecking behaviour, but it greatly reduces the damage resulting from the behaviour. In free-range and organic laying hens, flocks which were not beak trimmed during rearing were significantly more likely to show cannibalism (Lambton et al., 2023). However, the effect of beak trimming on reducing pecking injuries can be different between poultry genotypes. In a study of two commercial genotypes of turkeys (A and B), beak-intact toms from genotype B had a higher incidence of beak-inflicted injuries than

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beak-trimmed toms from genotype B (Noble et al., 1994). However, the incidence of injuries in genotype A was unaffected by beak treatment (Noble et al., 1994). However, as beak trimming impairs bird welfare (as the beak is highly sensitive and innervated, beak trimming results in pain and loss of function (EFSA, 2023)), this may not be a viable strategy in all EU Member States, particularly given that legislation on the practice ranges from longstanding ban to ongoing transitions toward ban, or its allowance as a routine practice. Beak trimming is not typically done in commercial broiler flocks due to the relatively low prevalence of pecking related issues.

Husbandry Factors (Environment and Management)

Rearing. Providing dark brooders during rearing is associated with a reduction of feather pecking and cannibalism in laying hens (Sirovnik & Riber, 2022). Additionally, laying hen pullets exposed to perches before their 4th week of age are less than half as likely to be cannibalised compared to birds that have not been exposed to perches by this age (Gunnarsson et al., 1999).

Stocking density. Lower stocking density may help to prevent or reduce the occurrence of SFP and cannibalism. Zepp et al. (Zepp et al., 2018) found that experimental groups of laying hen chicks with the same enrichment provision, but higher stocking density (22.9 vs. 18.1 birds/m²), showed higher rates of SFP. In broiler chickens, lower stocking densities elicit more exploratory behaviours (Blokhuys & Van der Haar, 1990; Hall, 2001) and consequently act to reduce the time spent pecking other birds.

Outdoor access and range. In organic and free-range laying hens, the risk of injurious pecking decreased as the number of popholes increased (Lambton et al., 2023). In addition to having a sufficient number of popholes opened, proper management of the area around the popholes can also help prevent severe feather pecking (Temple et al., 2017). Preventing rain from coming in through the popholes and having highly absorbent material (i.e., gravel, wood shavings) on the outside of each hole will help maintain indoor litter quality which can aid in preventing severe feather pecking. Popholes can be sheltered by a small roof on top of each one to reduce the appearance of contrasts in light between the inside of the house and outside.

In terms of poultry with access to an outdoor range, good range use by the birds may help reduce risk of behaviours like severe feather pecking by fulfilling behavioural motivations to explore and forage. Visible shelters should be placed close to the popholes to encourage birds out of the house. Easily accessible trees, shrubs, and dust baths should be present in the range. Pettersson et al. (2017) tested the provision of a “resource package” to 14 free-range laying hen farms in the United Kingdom. The package included objects intended to attract pecking (pecking pans with block, wind chimes) and a long narrow shelter outside the popholes that bridge the barren area close to the house. They found that this package reduced SFP and improved range distribution.

Enrichment. A detailed review on the effects of litter and enrichment on feather pecking behaviour has been provided by Schreiter et al. (2019). Providing high-quality pecking substrates (e.g., sand, peat moss) is suggested to protect against feather pecking by acting as an enrichment to encourage foraging and exploratory behaviour (reviewed in Monckton et al. (2020)). Blokhuys and Van der Haar (Blokhuys & Van Der Haar, 1989) found that provision of litter (compared to wired floors) at early ages substantially reduces later feather pecking in laying hens. Related to this, it has been suggested that providing manipulable materials (e.g., in the form of bedding/litter, or extra enrichment items) can aid in reducing SFP through diverting pecking behaviour. Green et al. (2000) found the absence of loose litter at the end of lay to be a risk factor for feather pecking in laying hens in alternative systems. Other studies have found that more manipulable substrate formats (i.e., long versus chopped straw, polystyrene blocks versus beads) reduced SFP (Huber-Eicher & Wechsler, 1998).

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Providing other relevant types of enrichment such as barriers, elevated structures, and ramps may help prevent severe feather pecking by providing opportunities for victims to escape (Estevez & Newberry, 2017). A study of turkeys found that the early provision (from day 3) of enrichment (e.g., chromed chains, supplemental UV light, and long-cut wheat straw) reduced pecking injuries compared to the control group (Sherwin et al., 1999). Pecking stones may provide an outlet for exploratory pecking behaviours. Some studies have found the provision of pecking stones (sometimes in combination with other enrichments) to be associated with lower mortality, reduced SFP, and better feather scores (Iqbal et al., 2020; Zepp et al., 2018). Some studies provide evidence that the use of pecking stones may serve to reduce beak length by blunting the tips (Baker et al., 2022), however this was not found to be the case in other studies (Iqbal et al., 2019).

Lighting management. There are some aspects of the light plan that can be used to prevent SFP and cannibalism. Bright spots (e.g. sun beams) may trigger birds to start feather pecking. Preventative measures should ensure an even light distribution without bright spots. Chickens can see the flickering of low frequency fluorescent lighting, which may be stressful. To avoid this, light sources should have either a high frequency (e.g. HF-FL) or no frequency (e.g. LED).

Other environmental factors. Environmental stressors such as inadequate temperature, ventilation, litter quality or noise may increase the risk of SFP developing. Therefore, continued monitoring of environmental conditions is an important aspect of prevention.

Nutrition

Nutrition research, mainly in adult laying hens, has shown that various nutritional strategies have potential to be used to prevent or reduce the occurrence of feather pecking and cannibalism. In a review of laying hen research, Mens et al. (2020) suggest that employing these strategies during rearing could help prevent feather pecking by affecting gut physiology and/or daily time budget (what the birds spend their time doing). Feed restriction can be a causal factor for SFP and cannibalism. Ensuring that birds are being fed the recommended quantity of feed on the recommended schedule, may help prevent or reduce instances of SFP and cannibalism. Additionally, minimizing the number of diet changes may help to prevent SFP by reducing stress to the birds (Temple et al., 2017). Low protein diets and diets deficient in certain amino acids like lysine, arginine, methionine, cysteine, and tryptophan (reviewed in (Kjaer & Bessei, 2013; Mens et al., 2020)) have been associated with increase SFP in (mainly) adult laying hens. Preventative strategies for broiler chickens could include ensuring that the amino acid profiles of the diet are appropriate to avoid SFP and cannibalism occurring as a result of a dietary deficiency. Other nutritional strategies to prevent or reduce SFP and cannibalism include feeding high-fiber diets, low-energy diets, or inclusion of roughages (Van Krimpen et al., 2005). These strategies aim to increase the time birds spend feeding or foraging and, consequently, reduce the time available to peck other birds. It should be noted that if the provision of low-energy diets is used, then it should be ensured that feed quantity is increased accordingly so birds are satiated.

Conclusions

Preventing cannibalism in poultry requires a multifactorial approach. There is a lack of research in to preventing cannibalism, but due to the close link between SFP and cannibalism, it can be assumed that similar prevention strategies may apply. While beak trimming can reduce the severity of injuries, it does not prevent injurious pecking behaviour, and its welfare implications and legal restrictions may limit its use. Instead, optimizing husbandry practices such as early access to perches, dark brooders, appropriate stocking densities, and well-managed outdoor access may help to

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reduce or prevent pecking behaviours. Environmental enrichments like manipulable materials, pecking substrates, and shelters, along with proper climate control could also be employed as prevention strategies. Additionally, nutritional strategies, including balanced amino acid profiles and high-fiber diets, can help mitigate pecking by promoting satiety and natural foraging behaviours.

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